

ROLE OF VAMANA KARMA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF URDHAVAGA AMLAPITTA: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Amlapitta is a disorder of the *Annavaha Srotas* and is commonly seen in the present era due to unhealthy dietary habits and improper lifestyle practices. The present case of *Amlapitta* was successfully managed with *Vamana Karma*, one of the important therapies among *Panchakarma* treatments. A patient of 30 year old was diagnosed with *Urdhavaga Amlapitta*, classical treatment according to *Ayurveda* text as *Vamana karma* was given. **Aim:** To evaluate the effect of *Vamana Karma* in the management of *Amlapitta Vyadhi*. **Materials and Methods:** This is a case study of *Urdhavaga Amlapitta*, where 30 year old female patient having symptoms of *Ura-Udardaha* (burning sensation in chest and throat region), *Tiktasyata* (bitter taste in mouth), *Tiktodgar* (bitter belching), *Pitta Udiran* (aggravation of Pitta Dosha), *Chardi* (vomiting) since 3 years. Symptoms were indicating confirmed diagnosis as a *Urdhavaga Amlapitta*. Patient was planned for *Vamana Karma* after *Pachana*. **Observation and Results:** Significant results were observed and symptoms of *Urdhavaga Amlapitta* were reduced. **Conclusion:** It can be concluded that *Vamana Karma (shodhana chikitsa)* is effective in *Urdhavaga Amlapitta*.

KEYWORDS: *Urdhavaga Amlapitta, Vamana Karma, Pachana, Pitta.*

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is one of the world's oldest holistic healing systems, based on maintaining a delicate balance between the mind, body, spirit, and environment. Good digestive health is essential for overall well-being and a healthy lifestyle. In *Ayurveda*, digestive strength is associated with the concept of *Agni*. According to *Acharya Charaka*, *Agni* is responsible for *Ayu*, *Varna*, *Bala*, *Swasthya*, *Utsaha*, *Upachaya*, *Prabha*, *Oja* and *Teja*.^[1] In *Ayurveda* it is said that रोगी स्याद्विकृते, मूलमग्निस्तस्मान्निरुच्यते^[2], which means *Agnimandya* is the root cause of all diseases. The primary causes of *Agnimandya* include *Adhyashana* (consuming food before the previous meal is digested), *Vishamashana* (taking meals at irregular timings and in improper quantities), and *Vegadharana* (suppression of natural urges), which ultimately lead to the vitiation of

Doshas.^[3] These are the factors responsible for *Annavaha Srotas Dushti*. *Amlapitta* is one of the disorders of the *Annavaha Srotas*. *Urdhvaga Amlapitta* is a *Kapha-Pittanubandhi Vyadhi* characterized by the predominance of *Kapha* associated with *Pitta*.

Kashyapa Samhita was the first text to mention *Amlapitta* as a separate disease entity.^[4] Apart from *Kashyapa Samhita*, *Amlapitta* is also mentioned in *Madhava Nidana*, *Yogaratanakara*, and *Rasaratna Samuchaya*. Although *Charaka*, *Sushruta*, and *Vagbhata* did not describe *Amlapitta* as a separate disease, symptoms similar to *Amlapitta* are mentioned under *Pittaja Grahani* in the *Grahani Adhyaya* of *Charaka Samhita*.^[5]

Madhav Nidan has described *Amlapitta vyadhi* in details, its aetiopathogenesis and symptomatology.^[6] There are two clinical types of *Amlapitta*, one is *Urdhvaga Amlapitta* while other is *Adhoga Amlapitta*.^[7] Common symptoms of *Amlapitta* are *Avipaka* (indigestion), *Tiktamlodgar* (sour belching), *Klama* (tiredness), *Udargauravta* (bloated stomach), *Utklesha* (nausea), *Hrutkanthadaha* (burning sensation in chest and throat region), *Aruchi* (loss of appetite).^[8] The *Lakshanas* of *Urdhvaga Amlapitta* are *Amlodgar* (sour belching), *Shirorooja* (headache), *Hrutakanthadaha* (burning sensation in chest and throat region), *Hastapadadaha* (burning sensation in upper and lower limbs), *Kwachita Jwara* (fever). Whereas in *Adhoga Amlapitta Dravamala Pravritti* (loose motions), *Daha* (burning sensation), *Murccha* (unconsciousness), *Trushna* (thirst), *Bhrama* (giddiness) are seen.

Repeated *Hetusevana* leads to vitiation of all three *Doshas* such as *Vata*, *Pitta*, *Kapha*, majorly *Pitta Dosh* is affected.^[9] The treatment of *Amlapitta* includes *Vamana*, *Virechana*, *Anuvasana* and *Aasthapana Basti*.^[10]

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

To evaluate the effectiveness of *Vamana Karma* in *Amlapitta*.

Case

Description

A 30 year old female patient presented to *Panchakarma OPD* with complaints of *Ura-Udardaha*, *Tiktasyata*, *Tiktodgara*, *Pitta Udiran*, *Chardi* for the past 3 years.

History of Present Illness: The patient had been suffering from the condition for the past three years.

Srotas Parikshan

Table 1: *Srotas Parikshan*.

Sr. No.	Srotas	Lakshanas
1	<i>Annavaha Srotas</i>	<i>Ura-Udardaha, Tiktodgara, Chardi, Pitta Udirana</i>
2	<i>Rasavaha Srotas</i>	<i>Tiktasyata</i>

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Centre of study: This study was carried out in *Panchakarma* Department of *Sane Guruji Arogya Kendra*, *Hadapsar*, *Pune*.

Treatment protocol: The patient was examined through detailed history taking and *Ashtavidha Pariksha* and was diagnosed with *Urdhvaga Amlapitta*. *Vamana Karma* was advised, as it is the first line of treatment for *Urdhvaga Amlapitta* according to *Bhavaprakasha*.

Vamana Karma: *Vamana* is one of the *Panchakarma* therapies in *Ayurveda* in which therapeutic emesis is induced to remove vitiated *Doshas* from the body. The treatment is carried out in three stages: pre-treatment, main treatment, and post-treatment.

During this period, she underwent allopathic treatment and experienced only temporary relief from the symptoms. As the symptoms persisted, she approached the Department of *Panchakarma* at *Sane Guruji Arogya Kendra*, *Hadapsar*, for further management.

Past History: No history of thyroid disorder, DM, or HTN.

Family History: No significant family history.

Personal History

Aaharaja - *Paryushit Abhishandi Aahar Sevan*, *Dadhi sevan*, Tea intake (3-4 times per day)

Viharaja - *Ratrojagarana*, *Diwaswapa*, Job in AC.

O/E

BP – 120/80 mmHg

PR – 80/min

S/E

CNS – conscious oriented

CVS - S1S2 normal

R/S – AEBE clear

P/A – mild epigastric tenderness

Asthta Vidha Pariksha

- *Nadi* - 82/min
- *Mala* - *Prakruta*
- *Mutra* - *Prakruta*
- *Jivha* - *Eshat Sama*
- *Shabda* - *Skapha Swara*
- *Sparsha* - *Snigdha*
- *Druka* - *Prakruta*
- *Aakruti* – *Madyam*

In the pre-treatment stage, medicines are given to improve digestion, followed by internal oleation, external oleation, and sudation therapy. The main procedure involves medicines that induce emesis. After the procedure, the patient is advised to follow a special diet regimen.

Intervention

Purva Karma - *Deepan and Pachana*

Following *Pachana Chikitsa*, the patient underwent routine blood investigations, chest X-ray, and ECG evaluation. Thereafter, informed consent for *Vamana Karma* was obtained from the patient.

Aabhyantar Aushadhi Sevan

1. *Sutshekhara rasa*:

Musta churn 2gm *Vyanodana* with *koshnajala*
Nirama lakshanas observed in 5 days.

2. *Abhyantar Vardhaman Matra Snehapana: Goghurut*

Samyaka Snehana Lakshana was achieved in 5 days as given below:

Snehapana Patra

Table 2: *Snehapana Patra*.

<i>Snehapana Day</i>	<i>Dose</i>	<i>Time of Snehapana</i>	<i>Time of Kshudabodh</i>	<i>Jarankala</i>	<i>Lakshanas</i>
1 st	30ml	6.45am	12.00pm	5hr 15 min	-
2 nd	60ml	6.45am	1.15pm	6hr 30 min	<i>Shirashool(alpa)</i>
3 rd	90ml	6.50am	3.00pm	8hr 10 min	<i>Hrulaas</i>
4 th	120ml	7.00am	4.30pm	9hr 30 min	<i>Twaksnigdhat</i>
5 th	150ml	7.00am	6.00pm	11hr	<i>Twaksnigdhat, Adhastad Sneha darshana, Snehadwesh</i>

During *Sneha Jiryaman* and *Sneha Jirna Lakshanas* observed and by going through it next day dose planned. On 6th day (*Vishram Din*) – *Sarvang Bahya Snehan* (Sesame oil) and *Sarvang Bashpa Swedan* was done. *Kapha Vardhak Aahara* was given to the patient in the night. (Medu Vada, Curd Rice, Black gram khichdi).

Pradhan karma After ensuring that the patient had attended to the morning natural urges of micturition and defecation, *Sarvanga Bahya Snehana* with Sesame oil followed by *Sarvanga Bashpa Peti Swedana* was carried out. Subsequently, 1 litre of milk was administered for *Aakanthapana*. Ten minutes later, *Vamaka Yoga* was administered to the patient.

Vamaka yoga - Apamarga Kwath 80ml
Madanphala Pippali Churn - 3gm
 Honey -10gm
Saindhav - 0.5gm
Vamanopaga Dravya - Yashtimadhu Kwatha

Nausea, sweating and abdominal bloating was observed in 25 minutes after consuming the *Vamaka Yoga*. After that *Yashtimadhu Kwatha* was given to the patient for easy *Vamana Yoga*. Vitals such as blood pressure, respiratory rate, pulse were checked throughout the *Vamana* procedure.

Vamana Patra

Table 3: *Vamana Patra*.

<i>Time</i>	<i>Consumed dravya</i>	<i>Quantity</i>	<i>Vomited Dravya</i>	<i>Symptoms</i>	<i>Vitals</i>
7.30am	Milk	1 litre			P-78/min BP-120/80mm Hg
7.40am	<i>Vamaka Yoga</i>		-	-	-
7.55am	-	-	-	<i>Swedapravrutti</i>	-
8.00am	-	-	-	<i>Udara Aadhmana</i>	P-82/min BP-120/80mm Hg
8.15am	-	-	-	<i>Hrullas</i>	-
8.20am	<i>Yashtimadhu kwatha</i>	2 glass (500ml)	1 vega	<i>Kapha, Dugdhapravartan</i>	P-94/min BP-130/90mm Hg
8.30am	<i>Yashtimadhu kwatha</i>	4 glass (1lit)	1 vega	<i>Sakapha kwathpravartana</i>	
8.40am	<i>Yashtimadhu kwatha</i>	2 glass (500ml)	1 vega	<i>Aushadhi pravartana</i>	P-98/min BP-130/90mm Hg
8.45am	<i>Yashtimadhu kwatha</i>	3 glass (750ml)	1 vega	<i>Tikta Aasyata, Pitta Pravartana</i>	
8.50am	<i>Yashtimadhu kwatha</i>	3 glass (750ml)	1 vega	<i>Katu - Tikta Aasyata, Shirashoola</i>	P-96/min BP-140/90mm Hg
8.55am	<i>Yashtimadhu kwatha</i>	2 glass (500ml)	1 vega	<i>Katu - Tikta aasyata ↓, shirashoola ↓, Udargauravata</i>	
9.00am	<i>Saindhava Jala</i>	2 glass (500ml)	1 vega	<i>Katu - Tikta aasyata ↓, Udargauravata ↓</i>	
9.15am	-	-	-	<i>Shareera Laghavata, Indreeya Prasannata, Prasanna mana</i>	P-76/min BP-120/80mm Hg
Total	-	5 litre 500ml	5 litre 800ml	-	-

Vamana Karma observation

- Vaigiki – 7 Vega
- Maniki – 300ml

(Consumed Dravya – 5 litre 500ml)

Vomitted Dravya -5 litre 800ml)

- Laingiki – Samyak Lakshana – Shareera Laghavata, Indreeya Prasannata, Prasanna mana, Shirashoola↓ Shuddhi Prakar – Madyama

Pashchat Karma

After completion of Vamana procedure, the patient was advised to wash his hands, feet, and face with warm

water. Dhumapana was given after 48 mins. Sansarjana Krama was advised for 5days (Madhyam Shuddhi) and told about Pariharya Vishaya.

RESULTS

- The present case was managed with Vamana Karma and was asked for follow up after 7 days. The patient was asked to come for follow-up after every six months.

Table 4: Results.

Sr.no.	Sign and Symptoms	Day 0	Day 7	Day 15	6 month	1 year
1	Ura-udardaha,	+++	+	-	-	-
2	Tiktasyata	+++	+	-	-	-
3	Tiktodgara	++	-	-	-	-
4	Pitta udiran	+++	-	-	-	-
5	Chardi	++	-	-	-	-

Where, Mild- + Moderate- ++ Severe- +++

DISCUSSION

Samprapti in patient was as follows,

Expulsion of Utklista Kapha and Vidagdha Pitta through Urdhva Marga

In the present case of Urdhvaga Amlapitta, the Vamana Karma possibly acted through mechanisms to break the pathogenesis of Urdhavaga Amlapitta.

- Deepana-Pachana was administered initially to correct Jatharagni, digest Ama, and convert the Doshas from Sama to Nirama Avastha. This reduced

further formation of Vidagdha Ahara and prepared the patient for Shodhana Karma.

- Abhyantara Snehapana produced Vishyandana, Dosha Utkleshana, facilitating the mobilization of vitiated Kapha and Pitta from peripheral tissues towards the Amashaya, the principal site of pathology in Amlapitta.
- Following Snehapana, Sarvanga Snehana further loosened and liquefied the morbid Doshas, while Swedana Karma promoted their movement from the Shakha to Koshta through dilation of Srotas and reduction of Srotorodha. Thus, adequate Dosha Utklesha was achieved.
- After proper Purvakarma, Vamana Karma was performed. Vamana directly expelled the Utklishta Kapha and Vidagdha Pitta through the Urdhva Marga, thereby eliminating the Doshas responsible for the disease. The expulsion of morbid Doshas reduced the excessive Amla, Drava, and Ushna Guna of Pitta, leading to relief from Tiktasyata, Tiktodgara, and Chardi.
- Further, Vamana resulted in Annavaha Srotoshodhana, restoration of normal Agni, and prevention of recurrent Vidagdha Ahara formation. By removing the root pathological factors, the upward movement of vitiated Doshas was arrested, thereby breaking the Samprapti of Urdhvaga Amlapitta.
- Thus, the combined effect of Deepana-Pachana, Snehana, Swedana, and Vamana Karma effectively corrected Agnimandya, eliminated vitiated Kapha-Pitta, purified the Annavaha Srotas, and provided significant symptomatic relief in the patient, confirming the efficacy of the treatment in achieving Samprapti Bhanga of Urdhvaga Amlapitta.
- After Vamana Karma, Samsarjana Karma was advised to gradually restore and enhance Agni. On follow-up after 15 days, all symptoms which were

present initially such as Ura-udaradaha, *Tiktasyata*, *Pitta Udiran* subsided completely without recurrence.

Shodhana Chikitsa helps in removing vitiated *Doshas* from the body and also prevents recurrence of the disease in the future.

CONCLUSION

Vamana Karma plays a significant role in the management of *Urdhavaga Amlapitta*, as it not only provides symptomatic relief but also helps in treating the disease from its root cause. By eliminating the aggravated *Kapha* and vitiated *Pitta Doshas* from their site of accumulation, *Vamana* corrects the underlying pathology of the disease.

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